

Software Development Best Practices WG

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OPINION ARTICLE
Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software [version 1; referees: 3 approved]

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4 OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE RECOMMENDATIONS HACKATHON

01-03 | AUG | 2018

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Top 10 metrics for life science software good practices

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From Design to DOI: Good Practices in Research Software

The aim of this lesson is to provide practical suggestions that contribute to making research software and its source code more discoverable, reusable and transparent. After the introduction, the following episodes of this lesson are structured in the form of one episode per recommendation. Hence the name four open source software recommendations. Note: This lesson materials are being developed in the open and are in current improvement.

Prerequisites
It is recommended that participants have some familiarity with GitHub, to create a public repository. Follow the Setup for instructions or partner with someone who can help you work on this part.

Schedule	Setup	Get ready, create a repository and create accounts if needed
00:00	1. Introduction	Why are best practices necessary in research software? How Open Source can help with better quality of software?
00:10	2. Make source code publicly accessible from day one	What are the benefits of making my software project public from the beginning? How do I make my project publicly accessible? What resources are available to help me document my software? What are the best practices in open software development? How do I publish my open source software?
00:10	3. Adopt a licence and comply with the licence of third-party dependencies	What a licence does? What is an open source licence? What is the importance of your licence for third-party dependencies?
00:10	4. Define clear and transparent contribution, governance and communication processes	How does someone start contributing to my project? What do I need to consider about project design and governance? How do people communicate within the project?
01:25	5. Make software easy to discover by providing software metadata via a popular community registry	Why are metadata important in research software? What are good metadata? Which are the most commonly used platforms for registering research software data?
01:45	Finish	

WP 2019 – 2021 Tasks

1. **Develop** specific **guidelines** to help software developers to adopt and comply with the 4OSS recommendations
2. **Train** and **promote** software best practices and the 4OSS
3. **Measure, recognize** and **visualize** adoption
(longer term aim)

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